

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5749386>

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:23293CA9-0138-4C1E-8C0F-111F27BCCAAB

New records of the short-winged mold beetles (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Pselaphinae) from the Dniester canyon of Vinnytsia Region

R. E. Krivosheyev

I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology

National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine

Bogdan Chmielnitski St. 15/2,

01030 Kyiv, Ukraine

ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-7319-1205>

E-mail: accipitergentilis777@gmail.com

Krivosheyev, R. E. New records of the short-winged mold beetles (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Pselaphinae) from from the Dniester canyon of Vinnytsia Region. — Ten Pselaphinae beetles are collected in the different points of Dniester canyon in Vinnytsia Region. All of them are recorded for the first time for the Vinnytsya Region.

Key words: Ukraine, Coleoptera, Staphylinidae, Pselaphinae, Dniester canyon, new records.

Кривошесєв Р. Є. Нові знахідки жуків-потаємців (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Pselaphinae) з Дністровського каньйону у Вінницькій області. У вінницькому Подністров'ї знайдено 10 видів потаємців. Усі вони вперше вказуються для області.

Ключові слова: Україна, Coleoptera, Staphylinidae, Pselaphinae, Дністровський каньйон, нові знахідки.

Introduction

The subfamily Pselaphinae was known to be represented by 126 species of 25 genera in the fauna of Ukraine (Krivosheyev, 2015). In Dniester canyon, several collections were made in Ternopil Region, in Dnistrovskiy Canyon National Park (Krivosheyev, 2018), but in Vinnytsia Region, there were no observations so far. In April 2021, more than five localities of dry steppe and forest locations near the Dniester River and its nearest tributaries were observed, and 10 species of Pselaphinae were collected. All of them are first recorded for Vinnytsia Region. All material collected by the author is deposited in the collection of I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, Kyiv (SIZK).

Brachygluta fossulata (Reichenbach, 1816)

Winkler 1925: 455; Löbl, 2004: 297

Material examined. Ukraine, Vinnytsia Region, Mohyliv-Podil's'kyi city vicinity, dry steppe slopes near Nemyia River, in grass and moss, 48.4719511 N 27.7930955 E – 2 specimens (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Almost the whole Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. The species dwells along riverbanks in forests and meadows (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Brachygluta haematica (Reichenbach, 1816)

Winkler 1925: 455; Löbl, 2004: 297

Material examined. Ukraine, Vinnytsia Region, Khon'kivtsi village, dry steppe slopes n. Karajets River, in litter and moss, 48.556356 N, 27.536312 E – 2 ♂ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Europe, excl. Scandinavia (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. The species inhabits forest litter and moss near the freshwater basins (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Bryaxis carinula (Rey, 1888) (Figs 1–2)

Winkler 1925: 460; Löbl, 2009: 16.

Material examined. Ukraine, Vinnytsia Region, Khon'kivtsi village, dry steppe slopes n. Karajets River, in litter and moss, 48.556356 N, 27.536312 E, 3 ♂, 5 ♀ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Central and Eastern Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Thermophilic species, inhabits dry warm slopes, hills and cliffs, often under stones (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Figs 1–2. *Bryaxis carinula*: 1 — male, habitus dorsal; 2 — aedeagus.

Bryaxis nigripennis (Aubé, 1844)

Winkler 1925: 459; Löbl, 2009: 18.

Material examined. Ukraine, Vinnytsia Region, Mohyliv-Podil's'kyi city vicinity, dry steppe slopes near Nemyia River, in grass and moss, 48.4719511 N 27.7930955 E, 5 ♂, 9 ♀ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK); ibid., Novodnestrovsk vicinity, Dniester River bank, in dry grass and moss, 48.609800 N, 27.441576 E, 7 ♂, 13 ♀ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK); ibid., Khon'kivtsi village, dry steppe slopes n. Karajets River, in litter and moss, 48.556356 N, 27.536312 E, 2 ♂, 2 ♀ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Centre, East and South-East of Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. The species occurs predominantly in beech forests, sometimes under the bark (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Bryaxis ruthenus (Saulcy, 1877)

Winkler 1925: 462; Löbl, 2009: 20.

Material examined. Ukraine, Vinnytsia Region, Mohyliv-Podil's'kyi city vicinity, dry steppe slopes near Nemyia River, in grass and moss, 48.4719511 N 27.7930955 E – 2 ♂ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Ukraine, Poland, Slovakia, Romania, Italy (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. The species inhabits coniferous and deciduous forests at the bottom of the mountains, in litter and moss (Roubal, 1930).

Bryaxis curtisii (Leach, 1817)

Winkler 1925: 462; Löbl, 2009: 16.

Material examined. Ukraine, Vinnytsia Region, Grabarivka village, deciduous forest along Dzhaglujka River, in litter, 48.517014 N, 27.714947 E, 9 ♂, 4 ♀ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Europe, excl. North (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter of all forests, under the bark and under the stones (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Bryaxis clavicornis (Panzer, 1809)

Winkler 1925: 462; Löbl, 2009: 16.

Material examined. Ukraine, Vinnytsia Region, canyon of Matirka River, n. Matsyorsk, deciduous forest near cliffs, 48.664697, 27.388940, 3 ♂, 1 female (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Northern and Central Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. The species dwells along the warm slopes of hills and mountains, often in moss and under the logs (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

***Bryaxis chaudiarii* (Chaudoir, 1845)**

Winkler 1925: 460.

Material examined. Ukraine, Vinnytsia Region, Mohyliv-Podil's'kyi city vicinity, dry steppe slopes near Nemyia River, in grass and moss, 48.4719511 N 27.7930955 E, 7 ♂ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK); ibid., Khon'kivtsi village, dry steppe slopes n. Karajets River, in litter and moss, 48.556356 N, 27.536312 E, 6 ♂, 7 ♀ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK); ibid., Novodnestrovsk vicinity, Dniester River bank, in dry grass and moss, 48.609800 N, 27.441576 E, 7 ♂ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Mediterranean and East of Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Thermophilic species, lives in grass and moss along the dry hills (own observations).

***Bythinus macropalpus* Aubé, 1833**

Winkler 1925: 462; Löbl, 2009: 16.

Material examined. Ukraine, Vinnytsia Region, Grabarivka village, deciduous forest along Dzhaglujka River, in litter, 48.517014 N, 27.714947 E, 4 ♂, 5 ♀ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Europe, excl. South (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Mesophyllic species, lives nearby the freshwater banks in deciduous forests (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

***Pselaphus heisei* (Herbst, 1792)**

Winkler 1925: 466; Löbl, 2009: 24.

Material examined. Ukraine, Vinnytsia Region, Mohyliv-Podil's'kyi city vicinity, dry steppe slopes near Nemyia River, in grass and moss, 48.4719511 N 27.7930955 E, 11 specimens (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK); ibid., Khon'kivtsi village, dry steppe slopes n. Karajets River, in litter and moss, 48.556356 N, 27.536312 E, 2 specimens (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Europe, excl. Italy, Portugal and Greece (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In grass, moss, swamps, under the bark and in forest litter (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Aknowledgements

I thank Halyna Stetsun and Valery Korneyev (I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology) for their assistance and advices for the microphotography.

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